

Entrepreneurship Education's Benefits to Motivate Prospective Teacher Students

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Abstract

In the current post-pandemic millennial economic situation, having knowledge about academic matters is no longer enough for active students or fresh graduates. Students are increasingly required to have skills and abilities that will increase their employability, such as: retrieval and handling of information; planning and problem solving; communication and presentation; and development and social interaction. With some basic backgrounds including living conditions, and cultural ownership, plus the existence of entrepreneurship education in the creation of new companies is an important aspect of this infrastructure, because it will encourage students to take risks starting a business. This study aims to determine the benefits of entrepreneurship education in motivating prospective teacher students at Bondowoso University to undertake entrepreneurial activities. To achieve the above objectives, a survey was conducted on 20 student teacher candidates. Data obtained through semi-structured interviews. The method used is descriptive qualitative method, which means data analysis based on facts. The results showed that 90% of student teacher candidates were motivated to carry out entrepreneurial activities in various fields such as buying and selling to agriculture. It can be concluded that entrepreneurship education can motivate prospective teacher students at Bondowoso University to engage entrepreneurial activities.

Keywords: *education; entrepreneurship; motivation*

A. Introduction

Nowadays higher education has a complex task to enable knowledge to solve real problems with emergent economic effect. Education Entrepreneurship has grown rapidly over the last two decades. Rapid developments in education provided by entrepreneurship, apparently given different arguments by several people. Some claim that entrepreneurship education can only be done when the entrepreneur carries out his business practices. A person who has an entrepreneurial character is always dissatisfied with something what he has achieved. Education entrepreneurship is important component of delivery stimulus to the individual to make a career choice, so increase the creation of new businesses and economic growth (Alhaji, 2015). Entrepreneurs are people who are skilled at using opportunities in developing its business with the aim of increasing his life. Evidence is rapidly growing that a great gap still existing between knowledge production and application might be successfully filled by entrepreneurship. The meaning of entrepreneurship is narrowed to the ability to create a

business plan, to establish an enterprise, or to start a business. However, broadly defined, entrepreneurship means the ability to create wealth; it also refers to the dynamic interaction between the individual and any opportunities in a given environment marked by a high degree of complexity and uncertainty (Neck, Greene, 2011; Dutta et al., 2011).

Hajizadeh and Zali (2016) analysed the impact of prior knowledge on entrepreneurial activities and concluded that it was an important issue especially in technologies; however, it could not be overestimated. Madsbjerg (2017) draws attention to knowledge within a social context:

- a. subjective knowledge (the world of personal opinions and feelings, a reflection of our inner lives);
- b. shared knowledge (our public and cultural knowledge; it involves sensitivity to our various social structures by capturing nuances such as mood);
- c. sensory knowledge (to some extent, it can be equated to sixth sense).

Rahmah (2017) said that social support will play a very important role in education individual entrepreneur, either social support that comes from colleagues and family who will be able to help a user get positive feedback for the education they carry out so that students can have for entrepreneurship

Figure 1. Model of the entrepreneurial university (Grecu&Denes,2017)

The image above presents the steps to implement an entrepreneurial mindset across campus to achieve entrepreneurial university. It all started with the commitment of university leadership and all staff. The next step is to create a structure that will coordinate and monitor implementation of the necessary steps. Increasing awareness of the importance of entrepreneurship, both for economy and for the future of the university is an ongoing process and must be targeted students, alumni, lecturers, administrative staff and the whole community and the business world. Everyone understands the need for short-term and long-term commitment entrepreneurship education. The execution mechanism refers to bidding of all stakeholders to implement plans to move forward towards university entrepreneurial approach.

There are five dimensions Entrepreneurship education namely: know what, know why, know-who, know how, and know when is the basis from entrepreneurship education: understand the purpose of an action, confidence and ability to influence personal environment as well develop that relationship positive with related parties (Johannisson, 1991).

The research question in this study is how is the role of entrepreneurship education motivating student teacher candidates in carrying out entrepreneurial activities at Bondowoso University.

B. Methods

The research method used in this research is using qualitative descriptive which is a form of research who use case studies in exploring the entrepreneurial process through higher education. Study collect data through in-depth semi-structured interviews with student teacher candidates. Data validity testing carried out with a qualitative analysis of this study using the technique triangulation of data sources. The research subject involves 20 student teacher candidates of faculty of teaching training and education at University of Bondowoso.

C. Results and Discussion

Entrepreneurship education is considered the fifth important factor of the twelve in the entrepreneurial ecosystem (Neck et al., 2018). This implies the role of the university as a key driver, especially at the initial stage entrepreneurial development. In many different studies, evidence-based data proves the role of education very important for entrepreneurs. However, there are consistent theoretical deficiencies background for systemic estimation of the impact that education can achieve entrepreneurial activity. Education is primarily considered as

motivation for coaching business-oriented entrepreneurship. An educational program is a valuable prerequisite for entrepreneurship when they are based on the integration of complex factors encompassing theoretical knowledge, competency development, and self-confidence development.

The growing attention to sustainable entrepreneurship is also worth looking forward to. However, researchers do not have a clear answer as to whether the same educational model can be equally effective for business-oriented entrepreneurship and sustainability. The results of our research from 20 prospective teacher students, 90% have motivation in carrying out entrepreneurial activities. Entrepreneurial fields that will be carried out include buying and selling and agriculture.

Table 1. The result of semi-structured interview

Students	Entrepreneurship Education	Experience in Environment	Do Entrepreneurship	Fields
R1	Yes	Yes	Yes	Agriculture
R2	Yes	Yes	Yes	Livestock
R3	Yes	No	No	-
R4	Yes	Yes	Yes	Catering
R5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Agriculture
R6	Yes	Yes	Yes	Agriculture
R7	Yes	Yes	Yes	Cake and Bakery
R8	Yes	No	No	-
R9	Yes	Yes	Yes	Agriculture
R10	Yes	Yes	Yes	Agriculture
R11	Yes	Yes	Yes	Cake and Bakery
R12	Yes	No	Yes	Agriculture

R13	Yes	Yes	Yes	Agriculture
R14	Yes	Yes	Yes	Livestock
R15	Yes	Yes	Yes	Agriculture
R16	Yes	Yes	Yes	Catering
R17	Yes	Yes	Yes	Agriculture
R18	Yes	No	Yes	Cake and Bakery
R19	Yes	Yes	Yes	Livestock
R20	Yes	Yes	Yes	Agriculture

D. Conclusion

There are two paradigms of methods and processes that coexist in relation to entrepreneurship education. The method approach is more suitable for educational contexts because it focuses on creativity, idea development, small actions, experiments; paradigm process lends itself to the development of corporate and business plans. Our research shows that in the initial experience of entrepreneurship students can recognize more factors with the characteristic of the method approach. Our research shows that students' motivation for entrepreneurship when they having no previous entrepreneurship education is very much based on opportunity. When they dealing with the complexities of reality, they need more than discrete competences or knowledge; moreover, they need it as an integrated phenomenon. We see common sense as an effective approach to responding to the changing surroundings of a living place with emergence sustainable entrepreneurship.

Our research implies that it is not difficult to start entrepreneurial activity without special education program. However, it is difficult to develop it and complete it successfully. Our experience shows that 90% of student teacher candidates are motivated to undertake entrepreneurial projects in various fields such as buying and selling to agriculture. Moreover, existing research shows that education can help students to have more entrepreneurial motivation and initiatives. Hence, we can state that there is a clear need for specialized entrepreneurship education in universities which will help have more initial projects, encourage getting started, and also succeed in future. Development of entrepreneurship education in

universities motivating the minds of the young generation to create entrepreneurship in sustainable development and meaningfulness.

Suggestions in this study are to pay attention to decision making research data with using a semi-structured interview instrument just describe statement which is not complete describe the truth the state of the respondent actually, then can suggested in research next process necessary data collection pay attention to the situation and conditions of accurate respondents such as conducting interviews as well as visits to each respondent's house. We hope this opens perspectives for new and challenging research. We suggest our conceptualization as a unique basis for further research with extension Sample.

E. References

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